

DELAMINATION ONSET PREDICTION BASED ON WEIBULL CRITICAL VOLUME METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Weibull statistical scaling of strength as a function of volume was used to predict free edge delamination onset in AS4/3501-6 laminates. Besides the Weibull integral method, Critical Weibull Volume (CWV) method was applied allowing one to identify the location of the failure onset, which in all cases occurred at the midsurface. The distribution of the transverse strength as a function of volume, which is required in the present method, is obtained in a separate set of testing involving 90° specimens. Thus the onset of delamination prediction is performed without the use of any empirical parameters, such as characteristic and/or average length. The delamination onset loads were predicted for a family of $[\theta/-\theta/\theta/-\theta/90]_s$ laminates for $\theta=15,20,25$ and 40, which were experimentally studied in [1]. B-spline analysis method was used for 3-D stress prediction to calculate the transverse normal stress distribution used for delamination onset prediction. It was shown that the delamination onset loads for $\theta=15$ laminates, which were predicted based only on mechanical stresses contributions were up to 30% higher than that by taking into account the thermal residual stresses. The predicted probability of delamination onset at a given load was very close to that obtained experimentally in [1] for all laminates when the thermal residual stress was taken into account.

KEYWORDS: delamination, strength, Weibull statistics, 3-D spline approximation, residual stress.

INTRODUCTION

Delamination onset and propagation investigation in composite laminates has been an application critical research topic for several decades and the subject of thorough review papers, e.g. Tay [2], Pagano and Schoeppner [3], etc. In the present paper we shall revisit the free edge delamination onset prediction in a family of tape composite laminates subject to axial tensile loading. Whereas accurate ply level stress analysis methods for generalized plain strain [4] and for general 3-D analysis with asymptotic enhancement near stress singularities [5] are well established, the delamination onset prediction methodology is still based on the application of average peel stress-type (over a ply thickness) approaches, as reviewed in [3]. The delamination onset prediction in the present work is based on the application of Weibull-based volume scaling of strength. The principal feature of the method is that the distribution of the transverse strength as a function of volume, which is required in the present method, is obtained in a separate set of testing involving 90° specimens. Thus the onset of delamination prediction is performed without the use of any empirical parameters, such as characteristic and/or average length.

WEIBULL SCALING OF STRENGTH.

Consider a population of test samples each having a volume V_0 and loaded so that the state of stress in each sample is uniform. Set σ the single stress component or a combination, such as the tensor polynomial function, which describes the failure mode of interest. Weibull weak link statistics is then based on the assumption that the probability of failure for a sample of similar specimens of arbitrary volume is

$$f(\sigma, V) = 1 - e^{-\frac{V}{V_0} B(\sigma)} \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) can also be generalized for nonuniform stress fields as

$$F = 1 - e^{-\frac{1}{V_0} \int B(\sigma(\mathbf{x})) dv} \quad (2)$$

where $dv = \det(\mathbf{J}) dx dy dz$ in Cartesian coordinates and \mathbf{J} is the Jacobian matrix. Integral (2) is derived by meshing the nonuniformly loaded specimen into an infinite number of infinitesimal specimens, each being loaded by stress $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$, which can be assumed constant within the mesh cell. The exponent in equation (2) expresses the probability of simultaneous survival of all mesh cells (each under a different stress), assuming that the probability of failure of each mesh cell is given by (1). Physically F can be interpreted as the probability of damage initiation anywhere in the volume of the specimen and therefore interpreted as an upper bound of the probability of failure. The integrand in equation (2) is generally a very nonuniform function of coordinates and often defined by contribution of only a small volume near the stress concentration.

Critical Weibull Volume

In this section we shall discuss the physical meaning of the critical or most likely local failure region in the presence of stress concentration. As mentioned previously integral (2) provides the probability of failure initiation, i.e. failure of an infinitesimal volume. We shall determine below the probability of failure of a finite volume and its size.

The failure or loss of load carrying capacity was defined only for uniformly loaded specimens as their apparent strength, described by distribution function (1). Transitioning to a nonuniform stress state is based on the assumption that the probability of failure P of a nonuniformly stressed specimen with stress distribution $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$ and the probability of failure (1) of the same specimen under uniform state of stress σ_u are related

$$P \geq f(\sigma_u, V), \quad (3)$$

if

$$\sigma_u = \inf_{\mathbf{x} \in V} (\sigma(\mathbf{x})). \quad (4)$$

The estimate given by eqn. (3) is not very useful when applied to the entire volume of the specimen. On the other hand, one can select a finite region in the nonuniformly loaded specimen, which has a volume V_i and minimum stress of σ_i , and calculate the probability of failure for this

subvolume $f(\sigma_i, V_i)$. Suppose that we have found a subregion with volume V_c and minimum stress σ_c , for which this probability is the highest, i.e.

$$f(\sigma_c, V_c) = \sup_i f(\sigma_i, V_i), \quad (5)$$

where index i scans all subregions of the specimen. Then the subregion V_c will have the highest probability of local failure, and we will call it critical Weibull volume (CWV).

Calculation of the CWV is easily performed by parametrizing the isostress contours obtained from the stress analysis. Consider a continuous function $v(q)$, $0 < q < \infty$:

$$v(q) = \text{vol}(V_q), \{ \mathbf{x} \in V_q \Leftrightarrow \sigma(\mathbf{x}) \geq q\sigma_0 \}, \quad (6)$$

where σ_0 is an arbitrary nonzero value of stress, which could be equal to applied loading or other finite value of stress depending on context. This function is equal to the volume of the specimen with stress higher or equal to $q\sigma_0$. In this case the CWV is

$$V_c = v(q_c), \quad \sigma_c = q_c \sigma_0, \quad (7)$$

where

$$f(q_c \sigma_0, v(q_c)) = \max_q f(q \sigma_0, v(q)). \quad (8)$$

The probability value (8) will be denoted f_c for brevity

$$f_c = f(q_c \sigma_0, v(q_c)). \quad (9)$$

Without limitation of generality one can assume that the stress distribution is continuous, which means that the function $f(q\sigma_0, v(q))$ is as well. Depending upon the stress distribution, which defines the volume function $v(q)$, this function can have a complex shape. For the problem at hand, which is the free edge delamination onset prediction, q is unbounded due to stress singularities present at the intersection of the ply interface and free edge. Asymptotic analysis of free edge delamination will be considered in the next section, as well as the conditions under which the Weibull integral (2) and the probability of local failure (9) are finite.

FREE EDGE STRESS SINGULARITY

Consider a dog-bone shape specimen, Figure 1, used for experimental study of the free-edge delamination onset in [1]. The contours of the curved edges of the specimen are described by the following parametric equation

$$x = c_1(s), y = \pm c_2(s) \quad 0 \leq s \leq 1 \quad (10)$$

where

$$c_1(s) = xL \text{ and } c_2(s) = c_2(-s) = \begin{cases} b, 0 \leq s < a_1 \\ k(s - a_1)^3, a_1 \leq s < a_2 \\ B, a_2 \leq s \leq 1 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Figure 1. Schematics of the free edge delamination test specimen in [1].

Asymptotic analysis of the singular stress fields arising near the intersection of the ply interfaces and the free edge is carried out similar to that performed in [4,5] in composites with circular holes. However, for the arbitrary contour of the edge the local coordinate system η, ϑ, ψ for asymptotic expansion will be defined by taking into account equation (10) as follows

$$x = \eta \cos \vartheta \cos \psi + c_1(s), \quad y = \eta \sin \vartheta \cos \psi + c_2(s), \quad z = \eta \sin \vartheta + z_p, \quad (12)$$

where z_p is the interface between p and $p+1$ plies and

$$\cos \vartheta = \frac{\dot{c}_2(s)}{\rho(s)}, \quad \sin \vartheta = -\frac{\dot{c}_1(s)}{\rho(s)}, \quad \rho(s) = \sqrt{\dot{c}_1^2 + \dot{c}_2^2}$$

The origin of the coordinate system (12) is at the free edge and ply interface intersection and the coordinate plane $\vartheta = \text{const}$ is perpendicular to the free edge, and the coordinate plane $\psi = 0$ is the interface between plies. The Jacobian of this transformation is

$$\det \mathbf{J} = \eta \rho(s) + \eta^2 \frac{d\vartheta}{ds} \cos \psi,$$

and requires a smooth contour with nonzero curvature ρ . Parametric equations (11) are approximated by using cubic spline functions to provide continuously differentiable equations for the free edge contour. Omitting details of the asymptotic expansion of the stress field for small η , described in details in [4,5] one arrives at the following representation

$$\sigma_{ij} = K(\vartheta) \eta^{\lambda-1} \sum_{k=1}^6 \gamma_k c_{ij}^{k,p} (\sin \psi + \mu_k \cos \psi) + o(\eta^{\lambda-1}), \quad (13)$$

where parameters $\gamma_k, c_{ij}^{k,p}$ and μ_k depend upon the relative ply orientation with regard to the normal to free edge contour, i.e. the coordinate ϑ but not the coordinates ψ and η .

A two-parameter Weibull distribution function is used in this study

$$B(\sigma) = \frac{\sigma^\alpha}{\beta^\alpha}$$

Other more complex distributions may be considered as well. Such distributions may be helpful to capture more sophisticated nonlinear size effects, i.e., where relationships between logarithms of average strength and size parameter are nonlinear functions.

To determine CWV as well as the probability f_c for stress distribution (13), we shall estimate the function $v(q)$ and define $q = \eta^{\lambda-1} \sigma_{ij} \Big|_{\substack{\eta=1 \\ \psi=0 \\ \vartheta=0}}$

$$v(q) \leq \pi L \cdot \int_0^q \eta \eta^{\lambda-1} d\eta = \pi L \frac{\eta^{\lambda+1}}{\lambda+1} \quad (14)$$

One can now calculate the right hand side of Eqn.(8) as

$$f = 1 - \exp \left[- \frac{\eta^{\lambda+1}}{\lambda+1} \frac{\eta^{\lambda-1} \sigma_{ij} \Big|_{\substack{\eta=1 \\ \psi=0 \\ \vartheta=0}}}{\beta^\alpha} \right] \quad (15)$$

Eqn. (15) yields $f=0$ for $\eta=0$ if $\alpha(\lambda-1)+\lambda+1 > 0$. This means that the CWV is nonzero. A similar condition can be obtained for the Weibull integral by substituting Eqn. (13) into (2). In this case one obtains that the integral in the argument of the exponent is bounded if $\alpha(\lambda-1)+2 > 0$. Since $0 < \lambda < 1$ for singular fields, the two conditions are indeed quite similar.

Thus the applicability of the Weibull scaling in terms of providing finite probability of failure in the presence of stress singularities is defined by condition

$$\alpha \leq \frac{1+\lambda}{|\lambda-1|} \quad (16)$$

As verified in the next section this condition is widely satisfied for multilayered polymer composites where $\lambda \sim 0.93-0.97$ and $\alpha \sim 10-12$ for the scatter of transverse properties of a composites.

Stress Analysis and $v(q)$ Function Calculation

Consider a dog-bone-shape laminated composite specimen, as shown in Figure 1. The laminate consists of N plies of total thickness H in the z-direction and has a length L in the x-direction and width A at the grips in the y-direction. The following displacement boundary conditions were applied to the specimen at the lateral edges $x=0,L$

$$\begin{aligned} -u_x(0, y, z) &= u_x(L, y, z) = \varepsilon_0 L / 2 \\ u_y(0,0,0) &= u_z(x, y, 0) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Traction-free boundary conditions were applied on all other surfaces. Dimensionless loading parameter ε_0 corresponds to relative elongation of the specimen. The transverse (z-direction) on

the bottom surface is constrained due to symmetric lay-up of the laminates considered, which allows one to model only half of the specimen. The constitutive relations of each ply are as follows:

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}^p (\epsilon_{kl} - e_{kl}^p \Delta T), p=1, \dots, N, \quad (18)$$

where C_{ijkl}^p and e_{kl}^p are elastic moduli and thermal expansion coefficients of the p^{th} orthotropic ply, and ΔT is the temperature change. Average applied traction was then calculated as

$$\sigma_0 = \int_{y,z} \sigma_{xx}(0, y, z) dy dz \quad (19)$$

To account for residual stress effects, two boundary value problems with different boundary conditions were solved. The effect of mechanical loading is accounted for by solving boundary condition problem (17)-(18) for $\Delta T=0$. Let us denote the stress field resulting from this solution at a unit applied load [Eqn.(19)] as σ_{ij}^M . The thermal loading problem for a given $\Delta T < 0$ (defined by the stress-free temperature), was solved under a different set of boundary conditions on the lateral sides

$$u_x(0,0,0) = u_y(0,L,0) = u_z(x,y,0) = 0, \quad (20)$$

which only restrict the rigid body motion. Denote the stress field resulting from this solution as σ_{ij}^T . The resulting stress field used for delamination onset prediction is obtained as a superposition as follows

$$\sigma_{ij} = \sigma_0 \sigma_{ij}^M + \sigma_{ij}^T \quad (21)$$

NUMERICAL SOLUTION

A B-spline displacement approximation approach developed by Iarve [6] was shown to provide highly accurate stress solutions including immediate vicinities of the ply interface and hole edge intersections, which result in singular stress behavior. Three-dimensional approximation is built by using the tensor product of one-dimensional approximations. Consider an elementary cube $[0,1]^3$ in local x_1, x_2, x_3 coordinate system, then the 3-D displacement approximation can be written as

$$\mathbf{u}(x_1 x_2 x_3) = \prod_i \prod_j \prod_k X_i(x_1) Y_j(x_2) Z_k(x_3) \mathbf{U}_{ijk} \quad (22)$$

where \mathbf{u} is the displacement vector and $\mathbf{U}_{i,j,k}$ are vectors of displacement approximation coefficients not necessarily associated with nodal displacements, and indexes i, j and k in equation (22) change from 1 to the total number of approximation functions in each direction. Depending upon the application and geometry, different orders of splines (from 1 to 8) can be used in each direction. Besides changing the order of splines, one can also change its defect (maximum number of discontinuous derivatives) in the node, thus being able to apply standard linear or a

higher order p-type finite element approximation if desired. Curvilinear coordinate transformation $\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}(x_1 \ x_2 \ x_3)$, $\mathbf{x}^T=(x,y,z)$ with Jacobian matrix $\mathbf{J} (x_1 \ x_2 \ x_3)$ is used to map the unit volume into the global x,y,z, coordinate system. The Gaussian integration procedure is used to calculate the components of the stiffness matrix. For purposes of the present study, we shall describe the procedure of calculating the overstressed volume function $v(q)$. After the solution is completed and all vectors $\mathbf{U}_{i,j,k}$ are determined, a post-processing step is performed when each integration point of the structure is examined twice. First the stress and strain components are computed, and the maximum value σ_m of the component of interest is found by searching through all integration points. A large number M (in our analysis M=101 and 201) is then prescribed, and a sequence

$$q_i = 1 - i/M, \quad i=0, \dots, M,$$

defined. The overstressed volume function $v(q)$ is then calculated in M points as

$$v(q_i) = \prod_{g_1} \prod_{g_2} \prod_{g_3} w_{g_1} w_{g_2} w_{g_3} \det (x_1^{g_1}, x_2^{g_2}, x_3^{g_3}) \eta(\sigma - q_i \sigma_m)$$

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